

CLIMAAX
climate ready regions

Annex 1

Flood risk assessment

MUNICIPALITY OF DOBRICH

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1. LOCATION OF DOBRICH-CITY MUNICIPALITY

Dobrich-City Municipality is located in the North-East planning region (NUTS-2) and is a constituent municipality of Dobrich District (Fig. 1). It covers an area of 109.1 km² (the smallest among the eight municipalities of the district).

Fig. 1. Dobrich Municipality on the map of regions in Bulgaria

Dobrich Municipality has a relatively balanced urban structure, characterized by different functional zones – residential neighborhoods of varying densities, industrial areas, green spaces, and agricultural lands.

The city has a compact shape, with approximate dimensions of 5.5-6 km in the north-south direction and 4.5-5.0 km in the east-west direction, covering a total urbanized area of approximately 20-22 km². The spatial structure of the city is radial-concentric, with several main functional zones: the central city part, residential districts, and industrial zones. The central city part is characterized by high density of construction, with low and medium-high administrative, commercial and public buildings (Fig. 2). Within its borders are the squares "Svoboda" and "Vazrazhdane", formed by the intersection of the pedestrian part of "25-ti

septemvri" blvd and "Bulgaria" and "Nezavisimost" streets. In the center of the Dobrich municipality are the Hotel "Bulgaria", the buildings of the Bulgarian National Bank, the Theater, the Art Gallery, the Concert Hall, the "Yordan Yovkov" Memorial House, and the Church of St. Great Martyr George.

Fig. 2. Satellite photo of Dobrich municipality

Residential neighborhoods, including Hristo Botev residential area, Balik residential area, and Dobrotitsa residential area, are situated in the central part of the city. A characteristic feature of the urban structure is the "Riltsi" district, a relatively independent urban unit located in the northwestern part of the city.

The industrial zones are located in the city's peripheral areas, with the Northern Zone being the largest in terms of area, followed by the Southern and Western Zones. The city's green system includes a city park in the southern part. The city has relatively few natural parks within the urban area.

A mosaic of different types of coverage is observed in the urban area, characterized by densely built-up areas with predominantly impervious surfaces in the central part, a more sparse structure with included green areas in the residential neighborhoods, and green areas along the river and in the peripheral areas (Fig. 3).

Figure. 3. Land cover classes in Dobrich municipality

The peri-urban belt is characterized by predominantly agricultural land use and arable areas of varying size and configuration interrupted by linear structures of transport infrastructure and industrial zones (Fig. 3).

Public spaces are hierarchically structured, including a central city square, a linear park along the Dobrichka River, and inter-block spaces in residential complexes. The city has a well-developed transportation network, including streets, boulevards, and a railway line.

Urban morphology features a well-balanced structure between the different functional zones, including residential neighborhoods of varying densities, industrial areas, green spaces, and agricultural lands.

2. NATURE OF THE MUNICIPALITY

2.1. Relief

Dobrich is situated on flat terrain, with slopes ranging from 1.5% to 6% prevailing. The maximum height of the municipality is 283.5 m (Dyadopeyova Mogila), and the minimum is 190 m, located in the riverbed of the Dobrichka River.

2.2 Climate

Dobrich Municipality is within the temperate continental climate subregion of the European continental climate region, with a temperate continental climate (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Climatogram of Dobrich City

Air temperature

The average annual air temperature is 10.2 °C. The maximum temperature is in July, with values close to those in August. The lowest average monthly temperatures are recorded in January and have negative values (Table 1). The annual temperature amplitude is 22.3 °C, typical of the temperate continental climate.

Table 1

Air temperature (°C) of Dobrich-city municipality

Indicator	I	F	P	A	M	Yu	Yu	A	With	O	H	D
Avg. temp.	0.5	2.3	6.3	10.8	16.1	20.4	22.8	22.8	18	12.4	7.9	2.5
Min. pace	-2.8	-1.5	1.8	5.9	10.9	15.4	17.7	17.7	13.5	8.5	4.6	-0.7
Max. temp.	4.1	6.3	11	15.8	21	25	27.6	27.9	22.8	16.7	11.6	6
Absolute min.	-22.7	-21.2	-18.3	-43.8	0	4.5	7.2	7.5	-0.2	-3.6	-14.3	-17.9
Absolute max.	17	20.6	27.1	31.5	36.5	34	37.1	39.1	39.1	33.8	28.3	19.3

The number of sunny days in the Dobrich Municipality varies from about five hours during the winter months to about 12 hours during June and July (Fig. 5).

Figure. 5. Number of sunny hours in Dobrich municipality

Air humidity and precipitation

The average relative humidity is 78%. The maximum humidity values, ranging from 85% to 86%, are recorded during the winter period, while the minimum values are recorded during the summer months, at 68-69%. The annual precipitation amount in the Dobrich municipality for a multi-year period is 537 mm, and the precipitation regime is typically temperate continental, with a maximum in June and a minimum in February (Table 2).

**Table 2
Precipitation (mm) and number of days with precipitation (°C) in Dobrich municipality**

Indicator	I	F	P	A	M	Yu	Yu	A	With	O	H	D	
Rainfall	40	35	35	46	51	56	47	39	42	39	55	52	537
Number of days with precipitation	6	5	7	8	8	9	7	5	5	5	5	6	

Maximum daily precipitation could reach 205 mm (Table 3).

**Table 3
Maximum daily precipitation (mm) with different probability**

H (m)	P= 0.1%	P = 1.0%	P = 5.0%
271	205.16	153.64	80.96
257	204.92	453.46	80.87
267	205.12	153.61	80.94

Winds

The wind regime in Dobrich exhibits characteristic seasonal dynamics, with higher values and more significant fluctuations during the winter months (December to February)

and relatively lower values and weak variations during the summer period (June to August). The region is characterized by a low percentage of calm weather, averaging about 20% per year. Northwesterly winds dominate, especially during the winter months, in contrast to the summer months, when the wind direction is more diverse (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. Wind direction and speed in Dobrich municipality in 2024

2.3. Water

The Dobrich River, a right tributary of the Suhata River, flows through the Dobrich Municipality's territory. The river originates from a spring located 278 m above sea level in the Kuza area (Fig. 7). Near the town of Dobrich, the river flows north, and after entering the

city, it forms an arc that protrudes to the east. Before leaving the urbanized area, it receives the waters of the so-called Severno dere, which also refers to the dry valley, characterized by water flowing in both river beds during rainfall and/or snowmelt. The Dobrichka River is 70 km long. It flows into the Suhata River about 2.0 km south of the village of Efreytor Bakalovo. The Dobrichka River has small water quantities and an unstable river flow. Hydrometric observations of the Dobrichka River – Dobrich (HMS No. 24), conducted from 1952 to 1965, reveal an average annual flow ranging from 0.01 to 0.09

Figure 7. Catchment area of the Dobrichka River

m^3/s (1953), with water in the riverbed present from May to June and in November–December. For the 13 years with historical data, water quantities in the autumn months are recorded episodically (e.g. in October 1957, July 1961, August 1962). The maximum monthly flow for 1952–1965 is $0.22 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, recorded in May 1953. The Dobrichka River catchment basin is asymmetrical, with a more developed left side, with an altitude between 191–253 m in its northern part and about 312–350 m in its southern periphery (Fig. 7). The configuration of the river catchment, the steep slopes in the upper relatively narrow part of the basin and their gradual decrease presuppose faster collection and movement of surface runoff during intense rainfall, and uneven distribution of river runoff.

Figure 8. Hydrogram of the Dobrichka River for 1952–1965

The water capacity of the river catchment varies between 0.01 and 0.33 l/s/km^2 , which explains the small and inconsistent water quantities in the river flow. The daily hydrograph of the Suhata River for 2000–2005 illustrates the significant variability in river runoff (Fig. 9). Dry spells and short-term inflows are characteristic of this region, which experiences unstable surface runoff.

Fig. 9. Hydrograph of the Sukhata River for 2000–2005.

In one of the left tributaries of the Northern Ravine, the microdams "Plachi Dol-1" (with a volume of $239,000 \text{ m}^3$) and "Plachi Dol-2" (with a volume of $149,000 \text{ m}^3$) have been built, intended for irrigation purposes. The catchment area of the two dams is 3.2 km^2 .

3. FLOODING DANGER

3.1. Flood map (baseline scenario 1980 and recurrence rate 1 in 250 years)

The 1980 flood map with a probability of 1 in 250 years shows minimum flood depths in Dobrich municipality ranging from -0.10 m to 0.10 m, suggesting a very shallow flood

Figure 10. Flooding retrieved from JRC for the area of Dobrich City

confined to a narrow corridor along the Dobrichka River (Figure 10). The limited extent of the flood (only along the river banks) is realistic, as the flat terrain and the lack of large tributaries limit the spread of water. The affected areas are mainly in the central part of the city, while neighborhoods such as "Riltsi" and "Pobeda" remain unaffected. The negative values (-0.025 to -0.100 m) likely reflect topographic depressions or limitations in modeling, which is typical

of older models based on 1980 data. The insignificant depths are realistic for this period but likely underestimate the risk, as the 1980 models did not account for future climate change and increased urbanization.

3.2. Potential for river floods, based on a 2018 base scenario and recurrence rates of 1 in 10, 1 in 50, and 1 in 100 years

In a flood with a recurrence period of 1 in 10 years, the height of the water layer varies from 0 to approximately 2.0 m, with the highest values (1.5–2.0 m) being recorded in the southern part of Dobrich, near the river. The majority of the flooded areas exhibit depths ranging from 0.5 to 1.5 m. The central and northern parts of the city appear to be less affected, with depths below 0.5 m or no flooding. In an extreme event with a recurrence period of 1 in 50 years, the water level reaches approximately 3.0 m in the southern parts of Dobrich, resulting in a broader flood extent compared to the 10-year scenario. The zones with depths between 1.5 and 2.5 m expand towards the southeastern and eastern parts, while the central parts remain with depths below 1.0 m. The flood covers a large area,

including the southern, southeastern and partly eastern regions of Dobrich. The center and northern parts are still less affected, but the risk increases (Fig. 11).

Fig. 11. River flood potential for a return period of 10, 50 and 100 years (2018 script)

A flood with a recurrence frequency of once every 100 years has a water table height of up to 4.0 m – significantly higher compared to the 1980 baseline scenario. Zones with depths between 2.0 and 3.0 m expand towards the eastern and southeastern parts, while the central parts already show depths of 0.5–1.5 m (Fig. 10). The flood covers a large part of the southern, southeastern and eastern regions and also begins to affect the central parts of Dobrich. The northern parts remain the least affected. This scenario is realistic, considering the increased intensity of precipitation and the rise in impermeable surfaces (asphalt, concrete) between 1980 and 2018, which reduces precipitation infiltration and increases surface runoff. This explains the broader scope and higher depths of the flood in the city center. The 2018 models likely utilize more recent climate data and more sophisticated hydrological models, which explains the higher depths compared to those in 1980.

Depths of 4.0 m are possible during extreme rainfall events, especially if the Dobrich River overflows and water accumulates in low-lying areas in the city center. Historical flood data in Dobrich, such as that from 2014, shows that heavy rainfall can cause significant flooding, although not as deep. This scenario is realistic but may represent a worst-case scenario if combined with other factors such as clogged drainage systems or simultaneous rainfall across the entire catchment area.

3.3. Flood potential in the 1980 baseline scenario and a recurrence rate of 1 in 250 years

Flood map for the baseline scenario (ca. 1980)
1 in 250 years return period
retrieved for the area of Dobrich-City

Figure 12. Flood map for the baseline scenario (ca.1980) 1 in 250 years return period

Floods in the 1980 baseline scenario and a recurrence rate of 1 in 250 years show a water table height of 0.00 to 0.10 m, which is consistent with the hydrological characteristics of the Dobrich River. In 1980, precipitation in the region was less intense compared to today's conditions. The limited extent of the flood, confined to the riverbanks, is realistic, as the flat terrain and the absence of large tributaries

restrict the flood's spread. The center of Dobrich is most affected, as the Dobrich River runs through the city's central parts, and the dense construction (even in 1980) likely increases surface runoff from precipitation. Neighborhoods such as "Riltsi" and "Pobeda" remain unaffected, which is consistent with their higher elevation and greater distance from the river (Fig. 12).

3.4. Flood potential under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios (2030, 2050, 2080, 1 in 250 years)

- *RCP4.5 (moderate scenario)*. This scenario assumes a mild increase in emissions and global temperatures, resulting in more intense precipitation, but with limited effects on smaller rivers, such as the Dobrich. Floods around 2030 (RCP4.5, 1 in 250 years) have water table heights ranging from 0 to approximately 0.4 m, with the highest values (0.3–0.4 m) concentrated in the southern and southeastern parts of Dobrich, particularly near the river. The majority of flooded areas exhibit depths ranging from 0.1 to 0.3 m. Flooding mainly affects the south and southeastern parts of Dobrich, following the course of the river. The

central and northern parts of the city are minimally affected, with depths below 0.1 m or no flooding (Fig. 13).

Fig. 13. Flood maps for RCP4.5 scenario, 1 in 250-year return period

Floods around 2050 (RCP4.5, 1 in 250 years) are expected to reach approximately 0.5 m in the southern parts of Dobrich, with a slight increase compared to 2030. Zones with depths between 0.2 and 0.4 m expand slightly towards the southeastern and eastern parts. The extent of flooding is somewhat more prominent than in 2030, but it remains limited to the southern and southeastern parts of Dobrich. The central and northern parts remain minimally affected (Fig. 13).

Floods around 2080 (RCP4.5, 1 in 250 years) reach water table heights of about 0.6 m in the southern parts of Dobrich, with a further increase by 2050. Zones with depths between 0.3 and 0.5 m expand towards the southeastern and eastern parts. The extent of flooding continues to increase but remains limited to the southern and southeastern parts. The central and northern parts remain with depths below 0.2 m.

- *RCP8.5 (high emissions)*. This scenario assumes a significant increase in emissions, leading to more extreme precipitation and higher river runoff peaks. Floods around 2030 in this scenario with a recurrence rate of 1 in 250 years reach heights of about 0.4 m, with the

highest values (0.3–0.4 m) concentrated in the southern and southeastern parts of Dobrich, close to the river (Fig. 14).

Fig. 14. Flood maps for RCP8.5 scenario, 1 in 250-year return period (relative to 1980)

The majority of the flooded areas exhibit depths ranging from 0.1 to 0.3 m. The flooding mainly affects the southern and southeastern parts of Dobrich, following the river flow. The central and northern parts of the city are minimally affected, with depths below 0.1 m or no flooding. An increase to 0.4 m is plausible but may be an underestimate, as RCP8.5 often leads to more severe flooding in flat areas. The extent of flooding should also be more significant, especially in the low-lying regions of Dobrich's center.

Floods around 2050 (RCP8.5, 1 in 250 years) are expected to result in water table heights of up to approximately 0.5 m in the southern parts of Dobrich, with a slight increase compared to 2030. Zones with depths between 0.2 and 0.4 m expand towards the southeastern and eastern parts, with the extent of the flood being slightly larger. Flooding continues to affect the southern and southeastern parts of Dobrich, with a slight expansion towards the eastern areas. The central and northern parts remain minimally affected, with depths below 0.2 m.

Floods in 2080 (RCP8.5, 1 in 250 years) have a water table height of up to about 0.6 m in the southern parts of Dobrich, with a further increase compared to 2050. Zones with depths between 0.3 and 0.5 m expand towards the southeastern and eastern parts, and some central areas already show depths of 0.1–0.2 m. The extent of the flood increases, affecting the southern, southeastern and eastern parts, with a slight penetration into the central areas. The northern parts remain minimally affected.

These scenarios appear less severe than the 2018 scenario (1 in 100 years, 4–5 m), which may be due to differences in modelling or the fact that a 1 in 250 year event is less frequent and may not reflect the most extreme rainfall events that are more likely in more frequent events (1 in 100 years). This suggests that the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 models may underestimate the risk, particularly for RCP8.5, where climate change could lead to more severe flooding.

3.5. Floods with different recurrence periods

A) The 10-year return flood map shows flood depths of up to about 2.0 m. The highest levels (1.0–2.0 m) are recorded in the central part of Dobrich, along the Dobrichka River. The majority of the affected areas show water table heights below 1.0 m. The extent of the flood is relatively small, which is consistent with the more frequent return period (1 in 10 years) and the limited flow of the Dobrichka River (Fig. 15).

B) The 50-year return period flood map shows an increase in flood depths, ranging from 0 m to around 3.0 m. The highest depths (2.0–3.0 m) are in the centre of Dobrich, along the Dobrichka River, with more significant flooding compared to the 10-year scenario. Flooding is still concentrated in the city centre, but the extent is wider, affecting most of the central districts. The central parts exhibit water table heights ranging from 1.0 to 2.0 m, while the Industrial Zone “North” is below 1.0 m. The extent of flooding increases compared to the 10-year scenario, as expected, given that the 50-year return period implies more extreme precipitation and higher peak runoff.

C) The 100-year flood map shows flooding with water table heights of up to 4.0 m in the most affected areas. Most of the central regions show depths between 3.0 and 4.0 m (Fig. 14). The flooding covers a wider part of the city center, where water table heights reach 2.0–3.0 m. The industrial zone “Sever” is more affected than in the previous scenarios, with depths ranging from 1.0 to 2.0 m. The surrounding areas, such as “Riltsi” and “Pobeda”, experience minimal flooding, with levels below 0.5 m. The extent of the flooding is

significantly more significant compared to the 10- and 50-year scenarios, which is consistent with the rarer and more extreme return period (1 in 100 years).

Fig. 15. Flood water depths for different return periods

D) The 500-year flood map indicates depths of up to 6.0 m in the most severely affected areas, with maximum depths located in the center of Dobrich, along the Dobrichka River. Most of the central regions show depths between 4.0 and 5.0 m, which is higher compared to the previous scenarios (10, 50 and 100 years). The flood covers a large part of the city center, with depths reaching 3.0–4.0 meters. The industrial zone “Sever” is more severely affected compared to the previous scenarios, with depths of flooded areas ranging from 2.0 to 3.0 m. In “Riltsi” and “Pobeda” the flood is below 1.0 m. The extent of the flood is significantly greater than that of the 10-, 50-, and 100-year scenarios, which is expected since the 500-year return period implies extremely extreme precipitation and runoff peaks.

In short:

- ✓ 10-year scenario: depths up to 2 m
- ✓ 50-year scenario: depths up to 3 m
- ✓ 100-year scenario: depths up to 4 m
- ✓ 500-year scenario: depths up to 5 m

Difference in flood height with a 10-year and a 500-year return period

The difference in the height of the water layer between two flood scenarios: a 10-year recurrence period (more frequent event) and a 500-year recurrence period (extremely rare and extreme event) is calculated as the depth in the 500-year scenario minus the depth in the 10-year scenario (Fig. 16).

Fig. 16. Flood height difference map with 10-year and 500-year return periods

- **Maximum difference:** The largest difference in depths reaches 3.0 m (red zones), which means that in these zones, the flood depth in the 500-year scenario is 3.0 m greater than that in the 10-year scenario. These zones are concentrated in the center of Dobrich, along the Dobrichka River.

- **Minimal difference:** In some areas the difference is close to 0 m (purple areas), indicating that the depths in both scenarios are almost the same. This is typical for areas less affected by flooding, such as the surrounding neighborhoods (e.g., "Riltsi", "Pobeda").

Negative values: There are areas with negative values (up to -1.0 m, dark blue), which may be due to topographic variations or modeling inaccuracies (Fig. 15). This suggests that in these areas the water height in the 10-year scenario is more significant than that in the 500-year scenario, which is unusual and likely a result of model limitations.

Affected areas

- **The center of Dobrich:** The most significant difference (up to 3.0 m) is in the central parts of the city, along the Dobrichka River. This is consistent with previous analyses that show that the center is the most vulnerable area in all scenarios (10, 50, 100, 500 years)

- **Industrial Zone "North":** The depth difference here is approximately 0.5–1.0 m.

• Areas such as "Riltsi" and "Pobeda" show a minimal difference (0 m), confirming that they remain less affected even under extreme scenarios.

Range of difference. The difference in depth is most pronounced in a narrow corridor along the Dobrichka River, which is expected since the river is the main source of flooding. The range of significant differences (over 1.0 m) is limited to the central parts of the city, while the surrounding areas show a more minor difference.

Summary: Flood depths and extent increase with increasing return period, which is expected since less frequent events (e.g. 1 in 500 years) are associated with more extreme precipitation and higher runoff peaks.

- 10-year period: water layer height up to 2.0 m, with a limited range, in the city center
- 50-year period: water table height up to 3.0 m, with a broader range affecting most of the central neighborhoods.
- 100-year period: water table height up to 4.0 m, with an even wider range.
- 500-year period: water table height up to 5.0 m, with the broadest range affecting a significant part of the city center and surrounding neighborhoods.

In summary, the flood hazard in a 10-year scenario is assessed as medium, and in a 500-year scenario, as high risk (Table 4).

Table 4
Flood risk assessment of the Municipality of Dobrich City

Parameter	Flood once 10 years old	Flood once 500 years old
Frequency	10% per year	0.2% per year
Probabilistic assessment	3 (high)	1 (low)
Depth (center)	6-8m	7-9m
Depth (periphery)	0-2m	1-3m
Scope	Areas around the riverbed	Almost the entire city
Rating	2 (moderate) Medium danger	3 (high) High danger

These results contrast with RCP4.5 and RCP8.5, where the extent remains limited to a narrow corridor along the Dobrichka River, with a slight increase by 2080. This supports the conclusion that the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 models may underestimate the risk, as they do not reflect the wider extent typical of extreme floods.

The models for the 10-, 50- and 100-year scenarios likely assume higher peak runoff and poorer infrastructure conditions, while the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 models may use more

average precipitation projections. Although a 1-in-250-year event is less frequent, we would expect greater depths under RCP8.5 due to more extreme climatic conditions. This suggests that the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 models do not adequately account for local factors, such as clogged drainage systems or increased runoff resulting from urbanization, which are more accurately reflected in the other scenarios.

4. EXPOSURE TO FLOODS WITH A 10- AND 500-YEAR RETURN PERIOD

Exposure is a key component in flood risk assessment and refers to the extent to which people, buildings, infrastructure and economic assets are located in areas at risk of flooding.

- Exposure of buildings and infrastructure: assesses the number and type of buildings, their construction, and flood resistance. This includes critical infrastructure such as hospitals, train/bus stations, police stations, fire stations, power grids, and water supplies. The assessment depends on the location and degree of impact under different flood scenarios.

- Population exposure: the number of people living or working in vulnerable areas, which depends on population density, socio-economic factors, and people's mobility. Vulnerable groups, such as children, the elderly, and people with disabilities, are at a higher risk.

- Exposure of economic assets: related to the value of affected industries, businesses and agricultural areas; depends on the possibilities for rapid recovery after a flood.

4.1. Exposure of buildings to floods and material damage

4.1.1. Infrastructure of Dobrich Municipality

The map displays a range of building types in Dobrich without categorizing them into primary categories (residential, commercial, industrial).

- Residential: apartments, houses, detached houses, semi-detached houses.
- Commercial: commercial buildings, offices, retail stores, supermarkets.
- Industrial: industrial buildings (industrial).
- Public: churches (church), hospitals (hospital), schools (school), government buildings (government), stadiums (stadium), synagogues (synagogue), and train stations (train station) (Fig. 17).

Fig. 17. Buildings before the classification of residential, commercial and industrial buildings

The map of classified buildings, categorised into four groups, reveals a predominance of commercial and residential buildings in the central and southern parts of the city, making them highly vulnerable due to the highest floodwater levels at all scenarios (Fig. 18).

Fig. 18. The classification of buildings into four main categories: residential (blue), commercial (yellow), industrial (purple) and universal (red)

Universal buildings are distributed evenly throughout the region, but are particularly visible in the center and southern parts (Fig. 19).

Fig. 19. Buildings Data with Unclassified Buildings as Universal Class

Including unclassified buildings as a universal class provides a more complete picture of risk, as it takes into account all buildings in the area, even those with an unclear function.

4.1.2. Exposure of key infrastructure ¹in Dobrich Municipality.

When assessing exposure to floods of varying frequency, a scale from 1 to 3 is applied as follows:

- 1 (low): The objects are in zones with a depth of 0–2 m, with low impact.
- 2 (medium): The objects are in zones with a depth of 2–4 m, with moderate impact.
- 3 (high): The objects are located in areas with depths exceeding 4 m, resulting in high impact.

The municipality's critical infrastructure is located with varying degrees of exposure to flood with a probability of occurrence in 10 years and in 500 years (Fig. 20). In both return periods, the hospital, fire station and police station have a high degree of exposure, and the railway station - a medium degree. In the 500 years, almost all critical infrastructure in

¹Critical infrastructure is indicated by different symbols: hospitals (red cross), train stations (green circle), fire stations (black "X"), and police stations (blue square).

Dobrich is exposed to significant flood depths, with the hospital, fire station and police stations in zones with a depth of 7–9 m, and the railway station - in a zone with a depth of 3–6 m. This significantly increases the risk to the functioning of critical infrastructure during extreme flooding.

Fig. 20. Exposure of critical infrastructure to river floods with a 10-year (a) and a 500-year return period (b)

The overall assessment in both analyzed cases remains high (Table 5).

Table 5
Assessment of the exposure of critical infrastructure to floods in the Municipality of Dobrich City

Recurrence period	Type objects	Flood depth	Exposure (1–3)
10-year period	hospital, fire station, police stations	6–8 m	3 (high)
	stations	2–4 m	2 (medium)
Overall rating		3 (high)	
500-year period	hospital, fire station, police stations	7–9 m	3 (high)
	stations	3–6 m	3 (high)
Overall rating		3 (high)	

4.1.3. Material damage to buildings during floods

The damage caused to buildings is determined based on the depth of the flood to which the buildings are exposed, using the following assumed values: CPI2010 = World Bank Consumer Price Index for 2010; CPI2022 = Consumer Price Index for 2022 for the respective country (most recent available value).

Damage classes:

- Options include residential, commercial, industrial, agricultural, cultural, transportation, and general purpose.
- In the standard code, agricultural, cultural, and transport buildings, as well as unclassified buildings, are designated as universal.

The damage function is based on polynomial functions fitted to the JRC depth-damage curves. The standard code applies a combined damage function based on the JRC depth-damage values for residential, commercial and industrial buildings.

The damage to buildings in the Dobrich municipality has been calculated in millions of euros in the four separate categories under different scenarios.

Damage to buildings in a 10-year flood recurrence period (calculated based on the average flood depth) ranges between 4.0 and 6.0 million euros and is concentrated in the central parts of Dobrich, especially around the Dobrichka River (Fig. 21). Damage to residential buildings and commercial properties located near the river is estimated at between 2.0 and 4.0 million euros. Economic damage in a 500-year flood recurrence period increases to 8–10 million euros in central areas and to 4–8 million euros in neighboring regions, with a larger area of flooded land.

Fig. 21. Damage (million euros) to buildings in river floods with a 10-year (a) and a 500-year return period (b)

Additional information is provided by the maps of buildings and river floods with a 10-500-year return period (Fig. 21) and the graph showing the expected damage to buildings based on the average flood depth and building locations (Fig. 22). In the 10 years, many buildings in the central areas are affected by depths of 6.0–8.0 m, in the 500 years the depth increases to 7.0–9.0 m, and the flooding also affects peripheral areas.

Fig. 22. Map of buildings and river floods with a 10-year (a) and a 500-year return period (b)

Fig. 23. Expected damage to buildings based on average flood depth and building locations

damage, probably because most buildings are already severely affected.

These damages are approximately as follows:

- 10-year period: around €60 million
- 50-year period: around €80 million
- 100-year period: around €90 million
- 500-year period: around €110 million

The average expected annual damage is € 7.77 million. This average value represents the expected damage over one year, considering all possible floods (with varying recurrence periods) and their associated probabilities. This value is helpful for long-term risk assessment and planning of protection measures.

The data provided (beyond those from the maps) on economic damage from floods with different recurrence periods show that residential buildings have the largest share in total financial damage, unlike industrial buildings (Table 6). These values differ slightly from those in previous maps (€70 million for the 10-year period and €115 million for the 500-year period), which is likely due to variations in the methods used for estimation.

Table 6
Expected damage (million €) to building classes in floods with different recurrence rates

Building class	Recurrence period			
	10-year-old	50-year-old	100-year-old	500-year-old
Residential	49.18	74.83	85.87	107.38
Commercial	2.83	4.46	5.37	6.27
Industrial	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Universal	6.20	9.65	11.37	13.40
Total	58.23	88.95	102.63	127.06

The degree of vulnerability ranges from low to high (Table 7).

Table 7
Assessment of damage and vulnerability of infrastructure to floods in Dobrich Municipality

Recurrence period	Type buildings	Damages (million euros)	Flood depth	Vulnerability (1–3)
10-year period	Residential	49.19	6–8 m (center), 0–2 m (periphery)	3 (high)
	Commercial	2.84	6–8 m (center), 2–4 m (middle zones)	2 (medium)
	Industrial	0.0	0–2 m (periphery)	1 (low)
	Universal	6.21	6–8 m (center), 0–2 m (periphery)	2 (medium)
General vulnerability		58.24	3 (high)	
500-year period	Residential	107.39	7–9 m (center), 1–3 m (periphery)	3 (high)
	Commercial	6.27	7–9 m (center), 3–6 m (middle zones)	2 (medium)
	Industrial	0.0	1–3 m (periphery)	1 (low)
	Universal	13.41	7–9 m (center), 1–3 m (periphery)	3 (high)
General vulnerability		127.07	3 (high)	

The damage of 49.19 million euros is substantial due to the significant damage to residential buildings, in contrast to commercial buildings, which are also located in the central area but are fewer in number. The damage of 6.21 million euros is moderate: some of the universal buildings are in the center, exposed to high depths. Industrial buildings are assessed with a low degree of vulnerability.

The lack of damage (0.0 million euros) is unusual, as the depths in the periphery reach 1.0–3.0 m over the 500 years. This may be due to the higher resilience of industrial buildings, the lower value of these buildings in the damage assessment, or error or omission in the data.

4.2. Exposure and vulnerability of the population of Dobrich municipality to floods

The population density in the town of Dobrich ranges from 0 to approximately 300 people, with the highest density (over 200 people) in the central parts of the region. The peripheral parts show lower density (under 50 people) (Fig. 24).

Fig. 24. Population density map 2025

The population exposure to flooding is calculated based on a population projection for 2025 and refers to areas where the flood depth is greater than 0.0 m. The population density exposed is expressed as the number of people per 3.0 arcseconds (approximately 90 m x 90 m at this latitude).

The initial information refers to the number of people exposed to flood risk and the number of people who must be evacuated in the event of a river flood. The sources of information – table, maps and graph- give significant differences in both indicators.

According to the table provided, the population exposed to flood risk is between 9344 and 12,290 people (Table 9).

Table 8
Number of population exposed to flood risk

Recurrence period (years)	Exposed population (number)
10	9344
50	10,072
100	10,085
500	12,290

According to the map data, the number of people exposed to flood risk is ~30,000 people with a 10-year recurrence period and ~50,000 people with a 10-year recurrence period (Fig. 25).

Fig. 25. Population and river flood maps with a 10-year (a) and a 500-year return period (b)

The data from the graph provides the following information:

- 10-year period: ~900 people
- 50-year period: ~950 people
- 100-year period: ~1000 people
- 500-year period: ~1200 people (Fig. 26)

Fig. 26. Population exposed to flood risk at different recurrence periods

The values in the graph are significantly lower than those in the table: for the 10 years, 900 people (graph) vs. 9,344 people (table), representing a difference of approximately 10 times; for the 500 years, 1,200 people (graph) vs. 12,290 people (table), again representing a difference of roughly 10 times. The data in the graph lead to a much lower exposure (1 – low), which would significantly reduce the risk assessment. However, these values seem unusually low compared to the previous maps and table, which show a much higher number exposed to flood risk. Since the graph does not provide additional context (e.g., an explanation of the methodology), the analysis proceeds with the data in the table.

The criteria for assessing population exposure (1 to 3) are as follows:

- 1 (low): less than 10% of the population is at risk, flood depth less than 1 m
- 2 (medium): 10–30% of the population is at risk, depth 1–3 m
- 3 (high): Over 30% of the population is exposed to danger, with depths exceeding 3 m.

With these criteria and a population of 87,361 people in Dobrich in 2024, the following results are obtained for the number of people exposed to the risk of flooding with different recurrence rates:

Table 9
Number of populations exposed to flood risk in different recurrence period (years)

Recurrence period	Number of populations at risk	Percentage of population	Flood depth	Exposure (1–3)
10-year-old	9344	10.70	6–8 m (center), 0–2 m (periphery)	2 (medium)
50-year-old	10,072	11.53	~6–8 m (center)	2 (medium)
100-year-old	10,085	11.54	~6–8 m (center)	2 (medium)
500-year-old	12,290	14.07	7–9 m (center), 1–3 m (periphery)	2 (medium)

Population vulnerability refers to the extent to which people can be affected by flooding – i.e. how easily they can suffer physical, social or economic harm. Since there is no data on vulnerability (e.g. age structure, health status, income), the number of evacuees is used as a proxy indicator: a high number of evacuees suggests high vulnerability, as the flood has had a significant impact on their homes and lives.

The maps for the displaced population (Displaced Population) for river floods with a 10-year and 500-year return period present this indicator through a color scale ranging from 0 to 17.5 people per 3 arches for the 10 years and from 0 to 20 people per 3 arches for the 500 years. The maps note the evacuated population in areas with a flood depth of more than 1.0 m. The most significant number of evacuees is projected to be in the central parts of the city, where the flood is deepest in both scenarios, followed by the neighboring urban areas (Fig. 27).

Fig. 27. Maps of the population that needs to be evacuated during river floods with a 10-year (a) and a 500-year return period (b)

An idea of the number of evacuees in the event of a flood with different probability of occurrence is given by the graph based on the population for 2025 (Fig. 28)

10-year period: ~700 people

50-year period: ~750 people

100-year period: ~800 people

500-year period: ~900 people

The average annual number of people evacuated during floods is 76.

Fig. 28. Expected number of evacuated populations for different flood recurrence periods

To assess the vulnerability of the population to floods with different recurrence rates, the relative share of evacuees (as indicated by the graph data) among the total population exposed to flood risk (as shown in the table data) is calculated. The relative share of the population that must be evacuated (of the population exposed to risk) is between 7.49% for a flood with a probability of occurrence once in 10 years and 7.32% for a flood with a probability of occurrence once in 500-years (Table 10).

Table 10
Number of population that needs to be evacuated

Period of repeatability	Population at risk		Population to be evacuated		Evacuated vs. at risk (%)
	Number	% of total population	Number	% of total number	
10-year-old	9344	10.70	700	0.80	7.49
500-year-old	12290	14.07	900	1.03	7.32

The combination of the physical and social vulnerability of the population gives grounds for introducing the following criteria:

Physical vulnerability:

- Depth over 3.0 m: Rating 3 (high), as it poses a direct risk to life.
- Depth 1.0–3.0 m: Rating 2 (medium).
- Depth below 1.0 m: Rating 1 (low).

Social vulnerability (based on displaced population):

- Over 50% of those exposed are displaced: score 3 (high).
- 20–50% of those exposed are displaced: score 2 (medium).
- Less than 20% of those exposed are displaced: score 1 (low).

In the case of overall vulnerability (the average of the two assessments), priority is given to physical vulnerability if it is higher, as it directly affects life and health.

This approach yields the following estimates:

10-year recurrence period:

- Physical vulnerability: Depth 6–8 m in the center → score 3 (high).
- Social vulnerability: 7.49% of those exposed are displaced. → Score 1 (low).
- Overall vulnerability: → 3 (high).

500-year recurrence period:

- Physical vulnerability: Depth 7–9 m in the center → score 3 (high)
- Social vulnerability: 7.32% of those exposed are displaced. → Score 1 (low).
- Overall vulnerability: 3 (high)

The final assessment of the risk for the population is determined by the three indicators: average risk in the event of a flood with a recurrence rate of once every 10 years.

5. FLOOD RISK ASSESSMENT IN THE MUNICIPALITY OF DOBRICH

5.1. Flood risk assessment for the infrastructure of Dobrich municipality

The flood risk assessment, derived from the previous hazard, exposure, and vulnerability assessments, indicates a high risk for a 10-year flood and a medium risk for a 500-year flood (Table 11). The combination of high exposure, high hazard, and high vulnerability led to significant damage (~60 million euros). For the 500 years, the risk is medium, as the low probability (frequency) reduces the overall risk, despite the high damage (~110 million euros).

Table 11
Flood risk assessment for the infrastructure of the Municipality of Dobrich City

Period	Exposure	Danger	Vulnerability	Risk (1–3)	Justification
10-year-	3 (high)	3 (high)	3 (high)	3 (high)	Risk = $3 \times 3 \times 3 = 27 \rightarrow 3$ (high). Residential buildings are highly at risk
500-year-	3 (high)	2 (medium)	3 (high)	2 (medium)	Risk = $3 \times 2 \times 3 = 18 \rightarrow 2$ (average). High vulnerability but low frequency

5.2. Flood risk assessment for the population of Dobrich municipality

The final evaluation of the flood risk for the city of Dobrich's population is medium risk (2) for floods with recurrence rates of 10 and 500 years (Table 12).

Table 12
Flood risk assessment for Municipality of Dobrich City

Period	Exposure	Danger	Vulnerability	Risk (1–3)	Justification
10-year-	2 (medium)	3 (high)	3 (high)	2 (low)	Risk = $2 \times 3 \times 3 = 18 \rightarrow 2$ (average)
500-year-	2 (medium)	2 (medium)	3 (high)	1 (low)	Risk = $2 \times 2 \times 3 = 12 \rightarrow 2$ (average)

The resulting difference in risk assessment for infrastructure and population is due to variations in individual indicators. Buildings are more exposed (3) than the population (2), as all buildings in the flooded areas are affected, whereas not all people in these areas are

directly at risk (e.g., those who live on higher floors). People have a more remarkable ability to adapt (e.g. by evacuating), which reduces the overall risk to them.

The small number of evacuated people (700 and 900 people) is inconsistent with the large flood depths (6–8 m and 7–9 m) and the large number of people (9,344 and 12,290) exposed to danger. It is possible that the graph and maps only cover certain parts of Dobrich, which underestimates the vulnerability of the urban population. The maps only consider the evacuated population at depths above 1.0 m and do not account for, for example, the number of people on ground floors or in areas with depths above 2.0 m. The depths of 6–8 m and 7–9 m suggest that all people in the center of Dobrich will be exposed to significant risk, which is not reflected in the low values for the displaced population.

6. Conclusions

River floods pose a significant risk to Dobrich, particularly over the 10-year period, where the overall risk is high (3) due to the frequency of the event and its substantial impact on buildings. Over the past 500 years, the risk is medium (2), reflecting a lower probability but still a significant impact. The high depths in the centre (6–8 m and 7–9 m) require special attention as they pose a direct risk to life, despite the low values for the evacuated population. The low values for the evacuated population may underestimate the actual number of people, especially in the centre. Additional data on population distribution (e.g. number of people on ground floors) would improve the analysis.

Which limitations of the datasets significantly affected the results?

1. Lack of data on water protection:

- The maps do not account for the presence of levees, drainage systems, etc., which can reduce the height of the water layer during floods, especially in the 10-year scenario. This can lead to an overestimation of the number of people at risk, the number of evacuees and economic damage.

2. Accuracy of population data:

The population estimate for 2025 is based on projections that may not accurately reflect the actual population density or distribution. This would affect the assessment of social impacts, including the need for evacuation and temporary accommodation.

3. Resolution of hydrological models:

Hydrological models used to calculate flood heights may have limited resolution, resulting in inaccuracies. For example, slight variations in topography (e.g. slopes, channels) may not be captured, which could affect depth distributions. This may lead to an overestimation or underestimation of this magnitude in certain areas, which will affect the assessment of damage and the number of people evacuated.

4. Lack of data on the value of buildings:

Economic damage is estimated based on JRC depth-damage functions; however, accurate data on the value of buildings in the area is lacking. If the value of commercial buildings in the center is higher or lower than assumed, the total damage may be inaccurate. This would affect the assessment of economic losses and average annual damage.

5. Climate models (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5):

RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 predict depths of up to 0.4 m, which leads to an underestimation of the risk compared to other data and, consequently, to insufficient flood preparation.